

The metabolism of *Dechloromonas* related microorganisms in EBPR systems

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Keywords: Enhanced biological phosphorus removal; Polyphosphate-accumulating organisms; Metagenomics; Multi-omics; Fluorescence in-situ hybridization

Summary of key findings

- The most abundant polyphosphate accumulating organisms found in the reactors were *Dechloromonas* and *Ca. Accumulibacter*.
- The presence or absence of key genes identified with polyP synthesis and degradation pathways were identified across all *Dechloromonas* genomes indicating a potential for polyphosphate metabolism.
- In all *Dechloromonas* genomes analysed, the central carbon pathway of TCA cycle, glycolysis and glyoxylate pathways were observed. Genes encoding the complete PHA accumulation pathway were also identified in all genomes, indicating a resemblance to the *Accumulibacter* PAO phenotype. However, genes for glycogen degradation and accumulation were observed only in some *Dechloromonas* species enriched in the bioreactors.
- A key difference in *Dechloromonas* cultures, compared to *Ca. Accumulibacter*, is that the low P release during the anaerobic phase can lower aerobic SRT requirement translating to high energy efficiency in full-scale EBPR processes.

Background and relevance

Phosphorus (P) is a pollutant but a non-renewable resource. Its removal is essential in aquatic environment protection. Its recovery also benefits in counteracting the depletion of the world P resources¹. The key microorganisms mediating the EBPR process is named polyphosphate accumulating organisms (PAOs)². PAOs have the ability to excessively store polyphosphate (poly-P) and use it as an energy source for the uptake and storage of carbon sources under anaerobic conditions. The stored carbon sources are used under aerobic/anoxic conditions for cell metabolism and growth. Meanwhile, excessive amount of phosphate is transported from the aqueous phase to cells and is stored as intracellular poly-P. This unique metabolic trait allowed PAOs to thrive the alternating anaerobic-aerobic/anoxic conditions.

Among these putative PAOs, there is a unique genus of microorganisms, i.e., *Dechloromonas*, which is closely related to *Ca. Accumulibacter* in the Rhodocyclaceae family. It seems that both PAO and glycogen accumulating organism (GAO) phenotypes occurred within this genus³. Our previous work also suggested that the existing *Dechloromonas* FISH probes do not well-combine some dominating *Dechloromonas* species in the bioreactors and WWTPs in Singapore⁴. Besides, previous study also suggested that some *Dechloromonas* may show a GAO phenotype in the EBPR system⁵. It is not clear whether these *Dechloromonas* are inherently GAOs or display metabolic versatility to glycogen-accumulating phenotype as shown in *Accumulibacter*⁶. In summary, in view of the wide-spread occurrence and the high

relative abundance values of *Dechloromonas* in WWTPs, it is necessary to further clarify their roles.

Materials and Method

To understand the biochemical characteristics of carbon and phosphorus cycling in *Dechloromonas*-related organisms and comparing it to *C. Accumulibacter*, cycle studies were performed during two phases of reactor operation – anaerobic and aerobic phase. Biomass concentration, nutrients and internal storage polymers were measured through the cycle. Genomic DNA was extracted using the Fast DNA™ 2 mL SPIN Kit for Soil samples and sequenced on a MiSeq (Illumina, CA, US) using a MiSeq Reagent kit v3 (2×300 paired end). New FISH probes for the *Dechloromonas*-related OTUs were designed and the specificity and coverage of the probes was evaluated together with existing *Dechloromonas* probes using TestProbe (<https://www.arb-silva.de/search/testprobe/>). *Dechloromonas* genomes analysed in this work have been previously published by Arumugam et al⁶. A pangenome analysis was performed to compare the metabolic potential of *Dechloromonas* from diverse lineages.

Results and Discussions

The most abundant EBPR related organisms found in the reactors were *Dechloromonas* (Fig 1 b), *Defluviicoccus* (Fig 1c) and *Accumulibacter* (Fig 1d). The changes in abundance of PAO and GAO species identified in Fig 1. is indicative of the ecological niche for anaerobic carbon uptake occupied by *Defluviicoccus* GAOs during the low DO phase whereas, and by *Dechloromonas* and *Accumulibacter* PAOs when DO was increased between 0.8 – 1.5 g/L.

The *Dechloromonas* pangenome analysed in this study comprised of 40% of the genes classified as core genome, while 28% of total genes were present only in any one of the *Dechloromonas* genomes and classified as singletons (Fig. 2). The presence or absence of key genes identified with polyP synthesis and degradation pathways were identified across all *Dechloromonas* genomes. The potential for polyphosphate metabolism is verified by the presence of low-affinity phosphate transporter (encoded by *pit*), which is identified to be vital for the PAO phenotype in supporting the export of cation (Mg^{2+} , K^{+} and H^{+})-phosphates under anaerobic conditions and generating proton motive force (PMF)⁸. High-affinity phosphate transporters (PstSCAB) were also detected in all *Dechloromonas* genomes analysed. PhoRB, a two-component phosphate transport system, was found in all *Dechloromonas* genomes except *C. D. phosphoritropha*. The presence of both low- and high-affinity phosphate transporters in *Dechloromonas* genomes may indicate both polyphosphate- and glycogen-accumulating metabolisms, akin to the metabolic versatility observed in *Accumulibacter* clade II members⁹.

In all *Dechloromonas* genomes analysed, the central carbon pathway of TCA cycle, glycolysis and glyoxylate pathways were observed. Genes encoding the complete PHA accumulation pathway were also identified in all genomes, indicating a resemblance to the *Accumulibacter* PAO phenotype. However, genes for glycogen synthase (*glgA*) and glycogen accumulation (*glgB*) were observed only in *D. aromatica* RCB, *D. phosphorivans*, *D. sp. AU3*, *D. phosphoritropha*, *D. agitata*, *D. sp. H13*, *D. phosphovourous* and *D. glycogenica*. Our comparative genomic analysis of *Dechloromonas* genomes reveals characteristic differences in genes responsible for signal transduction, chemotaxis, cellular processes and metabolism in *Dechloromonas* genomes implying the varied niches they occupy.

It is likely that the phosphorus cycling metabolism in *Dechloromonas* is similar to that of *Accumulibacter* and requires sufficient polyP storage for VFA uptake under anaerobic conditions. However, a key difference in *Dechloromonas* cultures is that the low P release during the anaerobic phase can lower aerobic SRT requirement translating to high energy efficiency in full-scale EBPR processes. This work enables the gain of a comprehensive and in-depth understanding of the roles of *Dechloromonas* related bacteria in EBPR systems.

Figure 1. Nutrient concentrations and relative abundance of key microorganisms involved in the EBPR process. (a) Phosphorus concentrations (mg P/L) at the end of anaerobic and aerobic phase during the period of reactor operation. Relative abundance of V1-V3 annotated ASVs for (b) *Dechloromonas*, (c) *Defluviicoccus*, (d) *Accumulibacter*, and (e) *Ca. Competibacter*.

Figure 2. The pangenome of *Dechloromonas* where genomes layers were organized based on the average nucleotide identity metric and the pangenome consists of 38047 genes organized into 11,189 gene clusters.

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